

DIABETES MELLITUS IN EVOLUTION: MAPPING GENETIC DIVERSITY AND THE HISTORICAL SHIFT TOWARD COMBINED NUTRITIONAL AND MEDICINAL MANAGEMENT

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18627324>

Keywords

Hyperglycemia, Genetics, Insulin Resistance, Diet, Good Health & Well Being

Article History

Received: 10 December 2025

Accepted: 25 January 2026

Published: 13 February 2026

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Abstract

Diabetes mellitus is a long-lasting metabolic disease that is and is due to chronic hyperglycemia caused by impaired insulin secretion, insulin response, or both. It is one of the largest international public health issues because of its increase in prevalence and consequential morbidity and mortality. There are several categories of diabetes mellitus, namely type 1 diabetes mellitus, type 2 diabetes mellitus, gestational diabetes mellitus, and other diabetes mellitus that deal with genetic or secondary factors. Treatment should be comprehensive and individualized, and it should involve lifestyle modification and pharmacological treatment to be administered effectively. Nutritional management is the base of diabetes management, which is vital in glycemic control, weight management, and complication prevention. The dietary approaches include balanced macronutrient consumption, portion, decreased intake of refined carbohydrates and saturated fats, and elevated intake of dietary fiber intake. Individualized nutrition should be followed to consider cultural inclinations, metabolic targets and comorbidity. Depending on the kind and the degree of diabetes, the treatment may be through medication. Insulin treatment is necessary for patients with type 1 diabetes and is often needed with advanced type 2 diabetes. Antidiabetic agents that are taken orally or by injections such as metformin, sulfonylureas, incretin-based therapies, sodium-glucose cotransporter-2 inhibitors are directed at various pathophysiological processes to deliver the best glycemic control. The combination of nutritional and medicinal approaches is essential to diabetes management in the long-term oriented treatment of a patient.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus, which is also known as diabetes, is a complex metabolic disorder which consists of hyperglycemia, an abnormal physiological condition in which there is a continuously elevated level of blood glucose. Hyperglycemia may be due to abnormality in insulin secretion or may be due to insulin action, sometime both and manifests in a heterogeneous and chronic manner such as carbohydrate, proteins and fat metabolic dysfunctions. Diabetes follows a complex pattern, varied presentations and pathogenesis [1][2].

Hyperglycemia and its associate metabolic dysfunction affect multiple organs in the body and cause them to affect their normal functions. These problems develop progressively and damage the small and large blood vessels that are essential for normal structure and function of organs. As the blood vessel damaged there is an appearance of microvascular and macrovascular abnormalities. These abnormalities cause organ damage, dysfunction and ultimately lead to organ failure in body, these organs include kidney, heart, eyes and nerves. Eye related problems result in retinopathy and ultimately lead to blindness. Kidney related problems result in nephropathy and result in renal failure. Heart related problems lead to hypertension and coronary heart disease. Nerve related problems lead to neuropathy which may be of autonomic or peripheral region. Autonomic neuropathy may lead to Cardiovascular, genitourinary (including sexual) and gastrointestinal dysfunction. While the long-term peripheral neuropathy includes foot infection (including ulcer), Charcot joint [3][4][5]

The peripheral arterial disease, coronary heart failure and cerebrovascular disease are termed as atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease [6] are most common with diabetes and constitute a major part of causing morbidity and mortality [7]

Diabetes with its gradual increasing global prevalence has emerged as one of the most challenging and important health issues worldwide. The increase in the prevalence of diabetes in countries is parallel to its rapid economic development. One cause is rapid urbanization and adaptation of modern lifestyle [8]

According to survey in year 2019 the number of diabetic patients aged between 20-70 years has been estimated to be 463 million, which was approximately 9.3% of world adult population of that time. It is estimated that by the year 2030 the number of diabetic patients may increase to 578 million, which is approximately 10.2% of the total world adult population and by the year 2025 it may reach 700 million, which comprises 10.9% of the world adult population. In year 2019 it seemed that there are 9.6% male and 9.0% females are suffering from diabetes [9]

It seemed that in year 2019 approximately 4.2 million people died (aged between 20-99 years) due to diabetes and its related complications. The total health expenditure on diabetes in the year 2019 is 760 million USD, which represents more than 10% of total spending on adults. Diabetes also effect woman with pregnancy effects more than 20 million live births which is estimated 1 in 6 live births in 2019 [10]. In 2006 WHO (Table 1) describe the criteria for diabetes [11].

Table.1 WHO criteria for diabetes Mellitus

CONDITION	2-hour glucose(mg/dl)	Fasting glucose (mg/dl)
Normal	<140	<110
Impaired fasting glycemia	<140	≥110 < 126
Impaired glucose tolerance	≥140	<126
Diabetes mellitus	≥200	≥126

One of the rising issue focuses on 2020 is the nutritional therapy of diabetes mellitus. This topic is of demanding concern because there is increasing number of diabetic patients worldwide. Type 2 diabetes mellitus that is closely related to obesity and overweight, people with unhealthy dietary choices and sedentary lifestyle [12][13]. The American Diabetic Association publishes on a yearly basis update on dietary sources for nutritional recommendation on diabetes [14]. The latest guidelines for nutrition were updated by the Europeans published in 2004 [15]. Many guidelines are present which generally follow the same recommendations. A consensus paper by the American Diabetic Association and European Association for the study of diabetes also provide the guidelines for dietary management [16]

Speaking of the guidelines of diabetes it is necessary to note that there is a considerable distinction between type 1 and type 2 diabetes as well that the type 2 diabetes is not a single disease in its phenotype and genotype [17][18]. The existing rules on diet therapy for diabetes are no significant distinction in the diet therapy of type 1 and type 2 diabetes. Whereas type 1 diabetes is an auto immune disease, which is brought about by severe or total defects in the insulin secretion. When there is type 2 diabetes there is a close association with the lifestyle of humans such as dietary factors, obesity resulting in being overweight causing insulin resistance in muscles, liver and adipose tissues [19]. It has appeared to characterize that type 2 diabetes is a heterogenic disease and that there are over 400 variants of this disease has been identified that elevate the prevalence of type 2 diabetes in majority of them seem to be associated with insulin secreting defects and many of them associated with obesity and insulin relationship also contribute to development of type 2 diabetes [20][21].

The end objective in the prevention of diabetes is to lower the blood glucose level of the body on

daily basis and prevent the long term and acute complications of diabetes that involve microvascular, macrovascular diseases and other long-term disabilities. A major challenge among diabetic patients in the globe in recent years is retinal disorders, cardiovascular disorders, and chronic renal disorders that are very common in recent years. Insulin therapy is applied in case of type 1 diabetes with close observation of glucose level in high-income countries. As time goes by, there is an emergence of various insulin injections, insulin pumps, and glucose-monitoring methods that lead to superior and sustained management of type 1 diabetes. Nevertheless, the healthy diet remains among the most effective ones in type 1 diabetes. Patients do not require special modifications in protein uptake with the exception of patients who have renal disease. Similarly to better, high-quality carbohydrates are better such that fruit, vegetables, whole grain products and pulses are better with patients. The consumption of carbohydrates must be within the recommendation limit on population [22-24]. Carbohydrate counting is significant and assists in the process of insulin therapy adjustment. The count of physical activity that the patient should have must be considered when calculating the carbohydrate intake of patient [25]. The consumption of sugar containing products must be careful (sugar less than 10%) because they have an impact on the body in both blood glucose control and in body weight control. The new sweeteners will have some extra advantages [26]. Concerning the intake of fats, quality and quantity must fall within the human lli general recommendation on the same regardless of the type of diabetes [27]. Since in both forms of diabetes the risk of atherosclerotic vascular disease increases, the dietary recommendation related to the intake of fats propose the consumption of unsaturated fatty acids rather than saturated ones (less than 7-10 percent).

Figure 1. Effect of Macronutrients in Diabetes progression

The habit of high protein diet is controversial in the current recommendation by American diabetes Association [14] and Diabetes and Nutrition Study Group [28]. The American diabetes Association also include some reservation for high protein use [29]. It was discussed earlier that the quality and quantity of proteins are not really a problem in case of type 1 diabetes but in case of type 2 diabetes higher intake of processed meat and red meat (Figure 1) products has been associated with the increased risk of type 2 diabetes and other non-communicable diseases [30]

The normal uptake of protein in diet is proposed by all the long-term trials of type 2 diabetes [31]. The major objective in the prevention of type 2 diabetes is attaining a permanent loss of weight that takes place through the implementation of healthy dietary patterns and by enhancing physical activity.

The research demonstrated that the weight loss can lead to remission of the recent type 2 diabetes [32] and the fat reduced pancreases and liver remarks of the weight control significance in both type 2 diabetes and prediabetic patients at the early phase of the stage [33][34]. Many techniques are available today to treat diabetes

like diet therapy, pharmacotherapy and insulin therapy. Several medications are available in market aimed at decreasing the blood glucose level by various mechanisms of action. These mechanisms include increasing peripheral glucose absorption by thiazolidinediones, increase insulin production by the effect of sulfonylureas [35][36], by delaying the glucose absorption in intestine and by reducing hepatic gluconeogenesis by biguanides [37][38]. There have been many studies done over the last three decades but there is no perfect result of diabetes treatment. One approach is the treatment of diabetes mellitus using medicinal plants. Many plants have active constituents like alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids and carotenoids. The antidiabetic treatment using medicinal plants may show increase insulin production in pancreatic tissue and reduce glucose absorption from intestine [39]

Types of diabetes mellitus

Diabetes mellitus is a complex condition and has a varied clinical presentation. The current classification explained is arbitrary and based on the pathogenesis and etiology of the disease and

useful in clinical assessment of disease for deciding the particular therapy [40].

According to this classification diabetes is divided into four main types (Figure 2)

- Type 1 diabetes mellitus
- Type 2 diabetes mellitus

- Gestational diabetes mellitus
- Associated with certain specific conditions.

Figure 2. Different types of diabetes

Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus

Type 1 diabetes mellitus is also known as insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus or juvenile diabetes mellitus. It usually occurs only 5-10% of the total cases of diabetes. It is characterized as an autoimmune disorder due to the destruction of beta-cell of pancreas by the action of T-cells. As beta-cells causing the secretion of insulin in body thus by destroying beta-cells the insulin level decrease ultimately led to hyperglycemia [41][42].

The pathogenesis of type 1 diabetes mellitus is not fully understood yet. But it is believed that the environmental and genetic factors play a vital role in pathogenesis of type 1 diabetes mellitus [43]. The rate of autoimmune destruction of pancreatic beta-cells and the rate of development of disorder is rapid in case of children and infants or may be gradual in adults [44]. There is a variability in the rate at which auto immune destruction of beta-cells occurs this often defines the eventual progression of the disease. For example, it is seen in cases in children and adolescents, there is sudden destruction of beta-

cells causing subsequent failure. This sudden failure led to diabetes ketoacidosis this often describe as first manifestation of the disease [45]. While in some cases the progression of the disease is very slow and the blood fasting glucose level increases slowly. This condition assumes severe hyperglycemic foam with or without ketoacidosis [46]. In some cases, it is seen that in patents including adult's beta-cells may retain some degree of function and be able to secrete an amount of insulin from pancreas this keep the patient safe from the prevalence of ketoacidosis. However, with the progression of the disease there is a deficiency of insulin, and the patient becomes insulin dependent followed by sever hyperglycemia and ketoacidosis. Despite various degrees of progression in type1 diabetes mellitus, the effected patient in the early stage, in the middle and in the later stage of life becoming severely hyper glycemc and insulin deficient and the proper survival of daily life is dependent on insulin [47][48].

Type 1 diabetes mellitus is an autoimmune disorder and characterized by many biomarkers (immune biomarkers), particularly autoantibodies. These autoimmune antibodies are related to immune mediated beta-cell destruction. These antibodies include.

- GADA (glutamic acid decarboxylase autoantibodies for example GAD65)
- ICAs (islet cell autoantibodies) for example ICA512
- IAAs (insulin autoantibody)
- Autoantibodies to tyrosine phosphatase
- ZnT8 (autoantibodies to islet specific zinc transporter isoform 8)

At least one of the above describe autoantibodies observe as biomarkers for diagnosis of type 1 diabetes mellitus. But usually more of these markers are observed in almost 80-90% of patients in case of new onset type 1 diabetes mellitus [49]

Insulin autoantibodies are important markers in the diagnosis of type 1 diabetes mellitus in children and infants however, its prevalence decreases with the age of onset increase. The presence of Insulin autoantibodies in person who has not treated previously with insulin is an important indication of development of type 1 diabetes mellitus. Insulin autoantibodies are

found in almost 70% of the children and infants at the time of diagnosis. Insulin autoantibodies play a crucial role in inhibition of functions carried out by insulin in patients with insulin therapy. This immune response is observed with various degrees of severity and found that almost 40% of patients on insulin therapy are found to be affected thus show different degrees of clinical manifestations [50]. The major majorities of the autoimmune antibodies (Table 2) are polyclonal IgG antibodies that vary in their binding capacities and affinity to the insulin. Insulin autoantibodies can be high insulin affinity/low binding capacity or low insulin affinity/high binding capacity. Clinical manifestations are caused by low binding affinity and high binding capacity of insulin autoantibodies. The association of these antibodies with insulin will result in slowing down or stopping the effect of insulin in the body and will lead to hyperglycemia in the patient. but which causes an excessive demand of insulin in the body, and a subsequent capricious hypoglycemic fit [51].

In addition to the destruction of the pancreatic beta-cells by the immune system there are numerous other autoimmune diseases which are reported to be more frequent in case of type 1 diabetes mellitus [52][53].

Table 2. Clinical and Pathological Characteristics of Organ-Specific Autoimmune Disorders and Associated Manifestations

Organ Involve	Autoimmune Disorder	Description	Reference
Adrenal Gland	Addison's Disease	Autoimmune Destruction of Adrenal Cortex to Cortisol Deficiency	[54][52]53]
Neuromuscular System	Myasthenia Gravis	Autoimmune Attack on Neuromuscular Junction Causing Muscle Weakness	[55] [52]53]
Git Track	Celiac Disease	Autoimmune Reaction to Gluten Causing Intestinal Damage	[56] [52]53]
Skin	Vitiligo	Autoimmune Destruction of Melanocyte Causing Depigmentation	[57] [52]53]
Blood	Pernicious Anemia	Autoimmunity Against Intrinsic Factor, Vitamin B12 Deficiency	[58] [52]53]
Thyroid Gland	Graves' Disease	Autoimmune Hyperthyroidism Due To Stimulating Antibody	[59] [52]53]
Muscle	Dermatomyositis	Immune Mediated Muscle Inflammation with skin Manifestation	[60] [52]53]
Liver	Autoimmune Hepatitis	Autoimmune Destruction of Hepatocytes Causing Chronic Liver Disease	[61] [52]53]

The autoimmune nature of this disease and its association with other autoimmune disease having a strong association with the human leucocyte antigen, its linkage to the DQA genes and DQB gene and direct influence by DRB gene. All these genes are present in hotspot gene region, and it is associated with the immunity response including autoimmunity. The genomic studies show that the strong association of this gene is linked with the HLA-DR3 and HLA DR4

haplotype and it is noted that this is strongly linked with DR4-DQB110302 haplotype which is associated with the destruction of beta-cell. In other diseases HLA haplotypes may decrease or increase susceptibility toward type 1 diabetes mellitus. [62-64].

Type 2 diabetes mellitus

Type 2 diabetes mellitus is also known as non-insulin dependent diabetes mellitus or adult-

onset diabetes mellitus. It is more prevalent type of diabetes and comprises almost 90-95% of the diabetes cases.

This type of diabetes is characterized by two abnormalities. [65-67]

- Insulin resistance
- Beta-cell dysfunction

Due to disruption of various pathways, there is development of insulin resistance in body, which leads to decrease in response to body toward insulin or decreases the sensitivity of cells in peripheral regions, particularly the liver, muscle and adipose tissue lose (Figure 3) its sensitivity against insulin. In the early stage of type 2 diabetes mellitus there is decrease sensitivity of insulin which triggers the pancreas beta-cell to increase the production of insulin which leads to the hyperfunction of pancreas to maintain a normal glucose level. Thus, the higher level of insulin in body prevents hyperglycemia. In these cases, gradually, the increase of the insulin production by beta-cells is not able to compensate for the requirement of insulin due to decrease sensitivity of insulin. By the continuous load the efficiency of beta-cell gradually declines and causing beta-cell dysfunction eventually leads to insulin deficiency in the body. In that case the normal glucose level cannot be maintained, and the body develops hyperglycemic stage. The secretion of insulin decreases but, in most cases, secretion is sufficient to prevent the body from diabetic ketoacidosis [68]. But due to stress conditions diabetic ketoacidosis may develop such as in other pathological conditions or associations with infection. Diabetic ketoacidosis may be precipitated by the use of drugs like SGLT2 (sodium-glucose co-transporter-2) inhibitors, antipsychotic and corticosteroids [69][70]. In the absence of any stress condition the patient with type 2 diabetes mellitus does not require any specific insulin therapy, at the time of onset or later throughout life [71][72].

The progression of type 2 diabetes mellitus is asymptomatic and extremely slow even to the extent that mild hyperglycemia develops with the passage of time and goes undiagnosed throughout the years until manifesting with

typical symptoms of severe hyperglycemia, blurred vision, polydipsia, polyuria, growth retardation, and weight loss in the late stages of the condition. This form of diabetes has a highly complicated pathogenesis composed of known and unknown factors. Such causes are genetic predisposition or environmental factors. The type 2 diabetes mellitus is more linked with the family history of diabetes, obesity, physical activity, modern lifestyle adaptation and aging. Apparently, it is more prevalent among individuals of some racial or ethnic background such as the Asian American, African American, Indian American, Latino and Hispanic. The presence of type 2 diabetes mellitus among such racial groups indicates that the first line blood connection and close by association with the genetic factors are strong but they are complicated and are not well defined. Contrary to the type 1 diabetes mellitus, there is no associated relationship that occurs in the auto immune or the immune mediated destruction of the pancreatic beta-cells [73][74]. Obesity is significant in the homeostasis of the glucose level of the body. Obesity leads to development of insulin resistance due to its effect of insulin sensitivity to tissue. It is, however, observed that the majority of patients with type 2 mellitus diabetes are obese and overweight although not all the patients are obese [75]. Obesity is defined as the rise in contents of fat in body which is one of the major factors in the prevalence of type 2 diabetes mellitus. The way it appeared is not the amount of fat but also the location of fat in the body determines the process of insulin resistance and consequently hyperglycemia. Indicatively, this type of diabetes has been closely linked with increase in abdominal fat in comparison with the increase in fat in the subcutaneous/gluteal or peripheral obesity [76]. It is highly linked to hypertension and cardiovascular diseases and lipoprotein metabolic abnormalities, which is defined by the high concentration of triglyceride and the low concentration of high-density lipids because of its close association with the fat type 2 diabetes mellitus [77].

Figure 3. Risk factors of type 2 diabetes mellitus

Gestational Diabetes mellitus

Gestational diabetes mellitus is described as the degree of intolerance of glucose or diabetes diagnosed during pregnancy. This type of diabetes usually occurs during second or third trimester. If a patient having undetected types 2 diabetes mellitus and detected during the pregnancy onset it is still called the gestational diabetes mellitus. However, the latest recommendation from International Association

of the diabetes and pregnancy study group excludes these criteria of diabetes diagnosed at the onset of pregnancy or afterward. If a woman with obesity is diagnosed with degree of insulin tolerance is described as previously undiagnosed diabetes rather than gestational diabetes mellitus (Figure 4). Gestational diabetes mellitus is different from preexisting diabetes as gestational diabetes may resolve after the termination of pregnancy or childbirth [78].

Figure 4. Mechanism of Gestational Diabetes

During early pregnancy (in first trimester) both fasting as well as post prandial blood glucose level are usually lower than the normal glucose level but in the third trimester of pregnancy blood glucose level increases. In many cases the increased blood glucose level may reach up to diabetic glucose level and this condition is referred as gestational diabetes mellitus. More than 90 % of all cases and complications related to glucose level during pregnancy occur are fall under gestational diabetic mellitus. The chances of development of gestational diabetes mellitus are about 1-14% of all pregnancies. And its occurrences are greatly influenced by the population under study. It is study that the occurrence of gestational diabetic mellitus is more influence in ethnicity, the prevalence of gestational diabetic mellitus is highest among Asian Indian, Middle eastern (Iranian, Syrian, Iraqi), Filipina, Chinese, Japanese, Korean and Aboriginal Australians. The prevalence is lower in black and lowest among non-Hispanic woman [79][80].

The risk of Gestational diabetes increases with the increase in obesity, age, any previous history of glucose impairment and previous pregnancy with large babies [81][82]. Gestational diabetes mellitus is also associated with the lifetime increase risk of development of type 2 diabetes mellitus. The regular and lifetime screening is required for any kind of glucose impairment, in

order to early diagnosis of type 2 diabetes mellitus [83-85]

Idiopathic diabetes

This type of diabetes is referred to as type 1 b diabetes or as ICA-negative diabetes. This is characterized by the varying degree of insulin deficiency, which may be severe and occur in episodic pattern contaminants with various degrees of episodic and severe diabetic ketoacidosis. These patients require insulin replacement therapy but the need for the therapy is not absolute because this may occur in episodic pattern. This type of diabetes may exhibit with strong of inheritance and observe in minority of patients, of African-Caribbean origin or Asian. The pathogenesis or etiology of this type of diabetes remain unknown [86]

Another genetic syndrome related to diabetes

Certain syndromes have high chances of causing diabetes, for example Klinefelter syndrome, Down syndrome, Wolfram's syndrome and turner syndrome. Wolfram syndrome is a genetic disorder inherited in a autosomal recessive manner . It is characterized by complete absence of beta-cells during autopsy and insulin-deficient diabetes. In addition to diabetes the patient may also exhibit other complications as part of this syndrome [87][88] as in table 3.

Table 3. Genetic syndrome related to diabetes

Other Specific Types	Brief Description	Example	Reference
Defect on beta-cell function	This condition occurs due to genetic mutation with multiple clinical symptoms that diverse the treatment approach. Some of them appear in infants while others in adulthood	Chromosome 20, HNF-4 α (MODY1) Chromosome 12, HNF-1 α (MODY3) Chromosome 7, glucokinase (MODY2) Chromosome 13, insulin promotor factor-1 (IPF-1; MODY4) Mitochondrial DNA Chromosome 2, NeuroD1 (MODY6)	[88]
Exocrine pancreases disease.	Various impacts on pancreas causing hyperglycemia like trauma, inflammation, tumor and other	Trauma & pancreatectomy Cystic fibrosis Fibro calculous pancreatopathy Neoplasia Pancreatitis Hemochromatosis	[87][89]
Genetic defects in insulin action	This is caused by genetic mutation and is characterized by profound insulin resistance. When the beta-cell cannot be able to compensate the insulin requirement thus diabetes occurs	Type A insulin resistance. Leprechaunism Lipoatrophic diabetes Rabson-Mendenhall syndrome	[88][89]
Endocrinopathies	Excessive secretion of hormones that antagonize the effect of insulin	Hyperthyroidism Cushing's disease Glucagonoma Aldosteronoma Acromegaly Somatostatinoma	[88][89]
Infection	Viruses have been linked with the destruction of beta-cell	Cytomegalovirus Congenital rubella	[88][89]
Chemical or drug induced diabetes	Certain drugs or chemical can interfere with the secretion of insulin	Glucocorticoids Thyroid hormone Alpha-adrenergic agonist Thiazides Dilantin Pyrinuron Interferon alpha	[89]

Immune diabetes form)	mediated (uncommon)	Rare mediated associated diabetes	immune disease also with	Stiff man syndrome Anti-insulin receptor	[87][89]
Another syndrome	genetic	Various arise chromosomal abnormality elevation of diabetes	syndromes due to causing risk of	Turner syndrome Wolfram syndrome Friedreich syndrome Huntington syndrome Down syndrome Porphyria Prader-Willi syndrome Myotonic dystrophy	[87][88][89]

Therapies for diabetes

Diabetes nutrition therapy

The patient with diabetes (rather type 1 or type 2) should be referred to as a registered dietitian for nutrition therapy at the time of or after diagnosis [90][91]. Another way is to refer the people for diabetes self-management education program that includes comprehensive instruction for diabetes management and nutrition therapy (Figure 5). However, many patients with diabetes cannot get proper structure education program for management of diabetes or nutrition therapy [92][93]. The national data concludes that only half of the patients with diabetes only gets proper education and even fewer consult to a registered

dietitian [94]. In a study of 18,404 people, it is concluded that only 9.1% of people had at least one consultation with a nutritionist within 9 years of period [95]. A study by institute of medicine concludes that the patients getting medical nutrition therapy have improved clinical outcomes and also possibly decrease the cost of Medicare to control diabetes. The Institute of Medicine recommends that the individualized medical nutrition therapy provided by a registered dietitian upon physical referral, be a covered Medicare benefits as a part of multidisciplinary approach to diabetes control [96]

Figure 5. Nutritional Therapy for Diabetes management

Medical nutrition therapy is an evidence based on nutrition care process, which is provided by a registered dietitian. This is the legal definition of nutrition counselling by a registered dietitian in the U.S [97]

Nutrition therapy is required in both types of diabetes mellitus as an effective component of overall treatment plan. Individuals with diabetes should get medical nutrition therapy to achieve the treatment goals. The therapy should be provided by a registered dietitian who is familiar with components and management of medical nutrition therapy. For the individual with type 1 diabetes mellitus there should be a flexible and intensive insulin therapy, education program to consult the carbohydrate counting meals and planning approach to control the blood glucose level [98][99].

The individuals having fixed insulin dose and balanced carbohydrate intake with respect to amount and time can result in improving blood glucose level and having less risk to develop hyperglycemia [100]. In patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus a simple meal planning such as

healthful food choices or portion control may be better suited. This may also be effective planning for older adults [101]. The people should get diabetes self-management education according to national standards when their diabetes diagnosed. Because nutritional therapy in case of diabetes is cost effective and improves outcomes. Nutritional therapy should be adequately reimbursed by insurance and other payers [102]. There is a common existence of hypertension and hyperlipidemia in patients with diabetes mellitus which requires proper monitoring of metabolic parameters like blood pressure, body weight, renal function, lipids [103]. Nutrition therapy designed includes the development of eating habits causing lowering blood glucose level, lowering blood pressure and management of lipid profile is important in the management of diabetes also in lowering the risk of cardiovascular disease, stroke and coronary heart disease (Table 4). Successful approach is to include physical activity to improve the lifestyle [90].

Table 4. Nutritional management of Diabetes

Nutrition	Recommendation and clinical goals	Rationale	reference
carbohydrate	Monitor intake to achieve glycemic control. Prioritize nutrition dense source like vegetables, fruits	Total carbohydrate amount is primary predictor of glycemic response; Low carb diet may improve A1C and lipid	[104][105]
Fiber and whole grain	Consume at least general public recommendation (14g/1000 Kcal) At least half of the grains are whole grain	Fiber associated with lower all-cause mortality Whole grain may reduce systemic inflammation and CVD mortality.	[104][106]
Sucrose	Minimizes the uptake. Can be substituted in an isocaloric amount of starch	Substituted up to 35% of calories does not negatively affect glycemia or lipid compared starch.	[104][107]
Fructose	Free fructose is acceptable if <12% of energy	Free fructose may be better control than sucrose	[104][108]
Nonnutritive sweeteners	It can reduce carbs intake if substituted for caloric sweeteners without compensatory eating.	Nonnutritive sweeteners do not produce glycemic effect	[104][109]
Total fats	Focus on quality of fat than quantity	Types of fat influence CVD rather than total fat	[104][110]
Plant stanol & sterols	1.6-3 g/day recommended in patient with dyslipidemia	Can reduce total LDL cholesterol. Efficacy is similar in those with or without diabetes.	[104][111]
Unsaturated fat	Recommend a Mediterranean style	Effective alternative to low-fat/high-carb diet.	[104][112]
Protein	Individualized goals Do not use protein to treat hypo glycemia. In cases with kidney disease do not restrict protein below usual intake	Protein increases glucose response but do not increase plasma glucose High protein diet 28%-40% show inconsistent results on A1C and CVD risk	[104][113]

Medicinal Therapy

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disease, which is caused by persistent hyperglycemia caused by insulin secretion defects, insulin activity, or both. The illness is generally categorized into type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM), type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM), and other special types, which are linked to genetic malfunction or secondary factors. Although lifestyle modification is fundamental in the management of diabetes, pharmacological treatment is the main focus in the attainment and maintenance of glycemic control, alleviation of complications, and enhancement of the quality of life [114]. The therapeutic treatment of diabetes has changed significantly over the past decades, and several classes of drugs were developed that act on various pathophysiological processes [115].

In type 1 diabetes mellitus, insulin is completely insufficient because of autoimmune damage of pancreatic β -cells. In turn, survival requires insulin treatment. The insulin preparation differs in terms of onset and duration of action to form a rapid-acting, short-acting, intermediate-acting, long-acting, and ultra-long-acting [116]. The insulin analogues, including insulin lispro, aspart, and glulisine, are often used to manage postprandial glucose excursions and the long-acting insulin analogues, including insulin glargine, detemir, and degludec, offer basal insulin cover. A basal bolus approach or insulin pumps are common in the current regimens of insulin [117]. The development of insulin analogues and insulin delivery systems has considerably lowered the chances of hypoglycemia and enhanced the level of glycemic regulation in people with T1DM [118].

Type 2 diabetes mellitus is typified by insulin resistance as well as an insulin secretion deficiency that is relative. Pharmacological interventions to manage T2DM are thus complex and they are meant to increase insulin sensitivity, stimulate insulin secretion, lower hepatic glucose production and lower intestinal glucose absorption [119]. The use of Metformin is universally advised to be used as the first-line pharmacological agent unless contraindicated. It

is a member of biguanide and is mainly decreasing hepatic gluconeogenesis and enhancing peripheral insulin sensitivity. Metformin is preferable because of its effectiveness, minimal chances of causing hypoglycemia, non-weight-gaining or slight weight-loss impact, and possible protective cardiovascular effect [120].

In case of failure to attain glycemic targets using metformin as the sole agent, other oral or injectable agents could be added. Sulfonylureas, including glimepiride, gliclazide and glibenclamide, produce an insulin effect by blocking potassium channels in pancreatic β -cells that are ATP-sensitive [121]. Although they can reduce blood sugar, their application is linked to the potential risks of hypoglycemia and weight gain, hence they are less preferable in some groups especially the elderly. Meglitinides, repaglinide and nateglinide, are similar but shorter acting with the better postprandial glucose control with slight less risk of hypoglycemia [122].

Pioglitazone is one of the thiazolidinedione (TZDs) that enhances insulin sensitivity in the adipose tissue, muscle, and liver through the activation of peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor- γ (PPAR- γ). These agents are capable of lowering insulin resistance, but they have been linked to undesirable side effects, which include weight gain, retention of fluid, increased chances of heart failure, and fracture of bones. Consequently, modern diabetes management has increasingly become selective in their use [123].

The incretin-based therapies are one of the important improvements in treating T2DM. GLP-1 receptor agonists, such as exenatide, liraglutide, dulaglutide, and semaglutide have been shown to increase the glucose-dependent insulin secretion, reduce glucagon release, delay gastric emptying, and increase satiety. These agents are also desirable in terms of their strong glucose-reducing effect, minimal risk of hypoglycemia, and considerable weight loss. Moreover, some GLP-1 receptor agonists are cardiovascular and renal beneficial, and this is

why they are more preferable to individuals with a known cardiovascular disease [124].

Sitagliptin, linagliptin, and vildagliptin are a few examples of the dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4) inhibitors that extend the lifespan of the endogenous incretin hormones by blocking their breakdown. In comparison to GLP-1 receptor agonists, DPP-4 inhibitors are not as potent, are taken orally, not weight gain, and have low hypoglycemia. They are combined with therapies that patients cannot take orally [125].

One more significant type is sodium-glucose cotransporter-2 (SGLT2) inhibitors, such as empagliflozin, dapagliflozin, and canagliflozin. The effect of these drugs reduces blood glucose by causing the urinary glucose excretion through renal glucose reabsorption inhibition. The secondary effect, i.e., weight loss, blood pressure lowering, and high cardiovascular and renal defensive properties, has made SGLT2 inhibitors more prominent. Nevertheless, they can predispose to genitourinary infections and in exceptional instances, euglycemic diabetic ketoacidosis [126]. Alpha-glucosidase inhibitors, including acarbose and miglitol, slow the rate of carbohydrate digestion and absorption in the small intestine, thus lowering glycemia levels after meals. Their clinical application is constrained by gastrointestinal side effects such as flatulence and diarrhea, yet it could be applicable in those patients with an overriding postprandial glucose increase [127][128].

With the progression of T2DM, most patients ultimately have to use insulin therapy as a result of the deteriorating β -cell functioning. Insulin is also started as basal insulin with oral agents, or over to full basal-bolus regimens. Timely insulin administration under suiting situations may enhance glycemic regulation and lessen the impact of long-term complications [129]. Pharmacological treatment is indicated in cases of gestational diabetes mellitus in cases where lifestyle interventions are not successful in meeting glycemic goals. The gold standard is insulin as it is safe during pregnancy. Under close medical control oral medications like metformin can be used in some specific situations [130].

To sum up, the pharmacological management of diabetes mellitus has become more personalized, based on the type of the disease, its prolongation, comorbidities, the risk of hypoglycemia, body weight, preferences of patients. It also led to a shift in paradigm of diabetes treatment because the growing range of antidiabetic medication has not only enhanced glycemic control but also the cardiovascular and kidney outcomes [131]. The best approach to management involves a patient-centered approach, frequent monitoring, and combination of pharmacotherapy and lifestyle modification in order to lead to sustainable long-term results [132].

Conclusion

Diabetes mellitus is a multifaceted and chronic metabolic syndrome that has a variety of different etiologies which are mostly grouped as type 1 diabetes mellitus, type 2 diabetes mellitus, gestational diabetes mellitus, and other specific ones. All of them are different in terms of pathophysiology, clinical presentation, and treatment needs, which requires an individual and holistic approach to management. The increasing incidence of diabetes in the world shows the necessity to have effective preventive measures and streamlined long-term care.

Nutritional management is also a guideline in the management of diabetes in all types of disease. Individualized dietary interventions with an emphasis on maintaining a balance of macronutrients, glycemic regulation, weight and cardiovascular risk minimization are more instrumental in enhancing metabolic outcomes and preventing complications. Regular nutrition therapy with physical activity would greatly increase treatment effectiveness.

There is a vast variety of therapeutic management with insulin therapy as a mandatory element of type 1 diabetes and at the advanced stage of the disease, oral and injectable antidiabetic therapy, aimed at insulin resistance, insulin secretion, and glucose metabolism. New breakthroughs in therapeutic approaches have enhanced glycemic control besides managing cardiovascular and renal complications. Finally, combining diabetes classification with the evidence-based approach to

nutrition and personalized therapeutic interventions is critical to the achievement of optimal glycemic control, the minimization of disease-related complications, and the improvement of the overall quality of life of the people living with diabetes mellitus.

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